

THE ROLE OF DEWEY'S PROGRESSIVISM THEORY OF EDUCATION IN AMELIORATING TANZANIAN NEW EDUCATION AND TRAINING POLICY (ETP 2014: 2023 EDITION)

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ABSTRACT

This article is mainly intended to highlight the contribution of Dewey's progressivism theory of education in improving Tanzanian New Education and Training Policy. For a number of decades since independence, Tanzania has been struggling diligently to establish an education system which could be more relevant to Tanzanians in the sense of responding fully to the needs and problems of Tanzanians. To pursue this goal and objective, Tanzania found itself in a challenge of making several review and reforms in Education and Training Policy (ETP) as well as curricula contents so as to have a more relevant education system though none of them seems to materialize. As a result, the government has decided to make a reform in ETP of 2014, which yield the new ETP of 2014: 2023 Edition. Being in the initial stage of implementation, majority of Tanzanians have a great expectation that the new ETP is going to provide solution to Tanzanian education challenges. On the other side, the article presents Dewey's progressivism theory of education as a means for ameliorating the new Tanzanian ETP. The theory focuses on practical education for solving social problems through promoting innovation, creativity, experiments, discoveries and effective utilization of natural resources for social benefit. Therefore, the article uses critical Hermeneutic method to assess the role of Dewey's progressivism theory of education in ameliorating the new Tanzanian ETP. Furthermore, Dewey's education theory has been an influential education theory in the discourse of philosophy of education and it has influenced the formation of different world education system in the modern and contemporary time.

KEYWORDS: Progressivism Theory of Education, Tanzania Education and Training Policy (ETP), Problem Solving Skills, Learning by Doing, Policy Reforms, Employability Skills.

INTRODUCTION

As a continuous effort to recognize the importance of relevant education system to its people, the government of Tanzania has taken various steps at different times to reform its education system so as to foster national development agenda. Despite those reforms in education policy, education stakeholders have been expressing various opinions and concerns regarding the adequacy and relevance of the policy's content and the curricula at different levels of education and training. Their main concern is that, Tanzania education system has failed to solve different social and national problems such as enabling graduates at different education levels to effectively utilize their human and natural resources for the betterment of the whole society as well as to use their acquired knowledge and skills to employ themselves or to be employed in different public and government

sectors. The government in response has launched the new ETP of 2014: 2023 Edition which is the result of the 2014 ETP reform. The new ETP holds majority's expectation and trust that the policy is going to provide solution to several identified educational challenges in Tanzania. However, the critical philosophical view shows that the new ETP has put much emphasis in the labor market demands and little emphasis on problem solving skills, innovation and creativity. Therefore, this article suggests the need to incorporate within the new Tanzanian ETP some Dewey's education ideas so as to ameliorate the policy to be more relevant to Tanzanian problems.

1.0 The New Tanzanian E. T. P

Since independence, Tanzania education system has passed through different phases with different education policy guiding all education issues in the country. Each education phase faced several

education dynamics that envisage the shift to another phase. The effort of the government to undergo several reforms in education and training policy was necessary and important for Tanzanians to have an education system which responds to their needs. Therefore, the new ETP of 2014: 2023 Edition which is now in the initial stage of implementation is the result of several reforms in ETP.

1.1 Reforms in Tanzanian ETP

Some remarkable reforms in Tanzania education policy extends from the first Tanzanian Education Act introduced in 1962 with the aim of ensuring that education is provided to most Tanzanian so as to prepare them to take position in different government offices following the vacancy left by the foreigners after Tanzanian independence.¹The major education policy in Tanzania was implemented in 1967 through the introduction ESR policy by the first president of the Tanzania, the late J.K Nyerere who aimed to prepare the learners with basic reliable skills and abilities for self-reliance.² Furthermore, education aimed to foster development and reduce a massive poverty brought by rapid change in political dimension soon after independence.³ Nevertheless, ESR policy faced several challenges during implementation such as “the unacceptability of the concept of education and work by parents/guardians, teachers and students and the persistence of the colonial education system’s influence in society.”⁴

The journey towards establishment of the 1995 ETP begins by establishment of Presidential Commission on Education in 1981. The commission had the task to review and assess Tanzanian education system then present recommendations from different education stakeholders on the new vision of education system for future.⁵ The commission lead to the formulation of 1995 ETP which addressed major changes in economic, political, cultural and technological sector

such as multiparty system, trade liberalization, privatization and others. Other policies introduced in line with the 1995 ETP includes: Technical Education and Training policy of 1996, the National Higher Education policy of 1999 and the information, communication and technological policy for basic education of 2007. All these policies ensured the smooth realization of the broader objectives of the 1995 ETP.⁶

In 2014 the government implemented another reform which yield the 2014 ETP. The 2014 ETP aimed to address various challenges within education sector such as to provide inclusive, equitable and quality education to all education level while aligning education with the labor market needs.⁷ Few years later in the initial stage of implementation the outcry from different education stakeholders heard claiming on the inadequate of the Tanzanian education system to copy with the demands of the modern time. This prompted the government to implement another reform which yield the new ETP of 2014: 2023 Edition.

The establishment of the new Tanzanian ETP was motivated by different education stakeholders such as, graduates, parents, politician, employers and others who in different times championed the need of the new ETP so as to meet the demands of the modern time socially, politically, economically and technologically. Furthermore, the demand was amplified by Her Excellence President of Samia Suluhu Hassan in her first speech to address the parliament of Tanzania on 22nd April 2021. Her Excellence articulated that; “my government will concentrate on review of the education and Training Policy of 2014 and making amendments to the existing curricula to make them skill-based consistent with the country’s environment and the global labor market.”⁸

One year later, the responsible minister of Education, Science and Technology Prof. Adolf Mkenda in his speech to the parliament articulated the beginning task of reviewing the 2014 ETP in the FY

¹MoEST, *Education and Training Policy 2014 - 2023 Edition.*, 1.

²Abel Ishumi and Suzgo Nyirenda, *Philosophy of Education: An Introduction to Concepts, Principles and Practice.* (Dar es Salaam: Dar es Salaam University Press Limited, 2002), 34.

³MoEST, *Education and Training Policy 2014 - 2023 Edition.*, 1.

⁴MoEST, *Education and Training Policy 2014 - 2023 Edition.*, 2.

⁵MoEST, *Education and Training Policy 2014 - 2023 Edition.*, 3.

⁶MoEST, *Education and Training Policy 2014 - 2023 Edition.*, 4.

⁷MoEST, *Education and Training Policy 2014 - 2023 Edition.*, 5.

⁸Bunge Polis, “Mkutano wa Tatu- Kikao cha Kumi na Tano- Tarehe 22 April, 2021.” (Dodoma: 2021), 170. <https://www.parliament.go.tz/polis/uploads/documents/1622533144-22%20APRIL, 2021.pdf>. accessed on: 17th May 2025.

2022/2023.⁹ In 2024 Prof. Mkenda announced the commencement of the of new ETP to primary schools especially standard one and two the same to secondary schools for only few shortlisted schools which have complete required infrastructure and personnel to support the implementation of the new policy especially vocational education.¹⁰ Therefore, the new ETP provides guidance to enhance the education and training system with the goals of providing diverse opportunities for education and training, delivering education of nationally, regionally, and internationally recognized quality standards, preparing a competent and skilled human resource in line with national priorities, and strengthening the effective management and operation of education and training in the country.¹¹ Furthermore, the new ETP highlights government's commitment to continue improving, expanding and establishing education infrastructures so as to accommodate the new education demands associated by an increase in enrollment numbers to all levels of education.¹²

The new Tanzania ETP shows some improvements in several important areas which has been notified by different education stakeholders to trigger education achievement in Tanzanian. One of the fundamental improvement observed is the recognition and integration of vocation education as an integral part of formal education recognizing the division of formal education into general education stream and vocation education stream. This increases diverse opportunities for learners to exercise their natural tendencies, interest, talents, and abilities in the formal system of education.¹³ Moreover, it provides a mechanism of recognizing, nurturing and developing student's knowledge, skills and competencies acquired outside the formal school system. The introduction of

vocation education in formal education system widen the chance for practical education whereby learners are able to exercise both theoretical and practical education.¹⁴ Additionally, the new Tanzanian ETP has incorporated the 21st century skills such as communication skills, problem solving skills, confidence, collaboration skills, creativity and critical thinking skills. The policy has encompassed other employability skills and technological skills for the sake of facilitating and improving performance in education sector.¹⁵

1.2 Critique On the New Tanzanian ETP

The new Tanzanian ETP has put much emphasis on education system that respond most to the labor market rather than a problem solving education system. Through different public information channels, government leaders in different times confesses on the need of reform in education which responds to the needs of the labor market. Professor Adolf Mkenda, the current Minister of Education, Science and Technology in Tanzania articulated before the national assembly that, "the government of Tanzania will continue to provide education system which will help graduates of every level to have knowledge that responds to the labor market."¹⁶ Nevertheless, the same word was repeated by Her Excellency Dr. Samia Suluhu Hassan the President of the United Republic of Tanzania during her first speech to the Parliament that: "...we will concentrate on review of the Education and Training Policy of 2014 and making amendments to the existing curricula to make them skills-based consistent with the country's environment and the global labor market."¹⁷ Moreover, education system for labor market does not seem to solve Tanzanian educational challenges because employment only solve economic problems.

Nevertheless, there is little emphasis on the learner's freedom and democracy to decide over their education interest and ambition in the new Tanzanian

⁹WyEST, *Hotuba ya Waziri wa Elimu, Sayansi na Teknolojia Prof. Adolf Faustine Mkenda (Mb)* Bungeni-2022, 106-107.

¹⁰WyEST, *Taarifa kwa Umma*, "Orodha ya Shule Zinazotoa Elimu ya Amali, Serikali na Zisizo za Serikali 2025"(Dodoma: 2025) Accessed from: <https://www.moe.go.tz/sw/taarifa-kwa-umma>. Accessed on: 18th June 2025.

¹¹MoEST, *Education and Training Policy, 2014, 2023 Edition*, 4.

¹²MoEST, *Education and Training Policy, 2014, 2023 Edition*, 63.

¹³MoEST, *Education and Training Policy, 2014, 2023 Edition*, 76.

¹⁴MoEST, *Education and Training Policy, 2014, 2023 Edition*, 9.

¹⁵MoEST, *Education and Training Policy, 2014, 2023 Edition*, 10.

¹⁶WyEST, *Hotuba ya Waziri wa Elimu, Sayansi na Teknolojia Prof. Adolf Faustine Mkenda (Mb)* Bungeni-2022, 107.

¹⁷Bunge tv Tanzania: "Rais wa Jamhuri wa Muungano wa Tanzania Samia Suluhu Hassan Kulihutubia Bunge la 12"

ETP. It is necessary to ensure that students are actively involved to provide their views on matters which concern them. Learners are not passive recipients rather they are important integral part in the of the learning proceedings. The new ETP does not clearly give information with regard to the platform which support learner's innovation, talents, abilities, interest and other psychological tendencies that may also influence their further education specialization. There is a need to have a special supportive environment with all necessary requirements such as equipment to facilitate innovation and discoveries for children so as to simplify their further education choices.

2.0 Dewey's Progressivism Theory of Education

The term progressivism was not firstly used by Dewey in his theory of education. It has been used differently by different philosophers from ancient time to date. Etymologically, the term originated from two Greek words which are "pro" to mean support and "gradi" which means to walk. Then, "prograde" can simply means support to walk. In English, therefore the term progressive means the forward movement towards a destination in space and time.¹⁸ Some notable thinkers who championed progressive theory in relation to education sector before Dewey are; Francis Bacon who advocated people to constantly seek for a new knowledge which are useful and to stop upholding knowledge which seems not to be useful. In *the New Organon*, Bacon contends that "useful knowledge is foundation for human power and human greatness."¹⁹ Charles Darwin in evolution theory insists that human society always evolve from simple to complex, hence the socio-political and economic systems ought to change so as to accommodate the new needs of man in of the society for their survival. Thus, education system too as among of the social system should change so as to respond fully to the new needs of man in the society.²⁰ Rousseau being quoted

by Darling and Ordenbo in their article titled 'Progressivism' advocates that what is taught or learnt should depend on the change of human experience, apparently, the experience of the learner should be valued and be center for learning rather than what the teacher dictates.²¹

Dewey's progressivism theory of education is directly connected to pragmatic philosophical approach, whereby education is purposely to support positive progress to the learners and not otherwise. Dewey suggest a problem solving education system, that learners must learn what they experience in their daily life.²² His education theory is centered on his famous quote that "education is not preparation for life rather it is the life itself,"²³ to mean that education must be designed in the way that learners become the active agents of their learning and not just passive recipients of knowledge. Learning must be an experience and reflection of what real goes around the learner's social setting. Education must be determined by psychological motivation in which the child's instincts and power act as a starting point for the process of learning. This save as the efforts of the educator connect with some activity which the child is carrying on of his own initiative independent of the educator. On the other side, sociological motivation acts as a platform for children to reveal their instincts, tendencies and talents.²⁴

Dewey insists the curriculum to consider five main principles which are: **Learning by doing**, this is the experiential learning style where by learners are exposed to the real life situations as part of their learning progress so as to acquire relevant skills, knowledge, techniques and abilities in solving different social problems. In this learning style, learners must engage in practical education through constructing tangible product from the theory gained in class.²⁵ The second principle is **Interdisciplinary**,

¹⁸Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, 9th ed., s.v. "progress," (London: Oxford University Press, 2015). Accessed on 12 June 2025, <https://oxford-advanced-learnersdict.en.softonic.com/android>.

¹⁹Francis Bacon, *The New Organon*, ed. Lisa Jardine and Michael Silverthorne (New York: Cambridge University, 2003), 90. (Hereafter will be referred as: Bacon, *New Organon*)

²⁰Charles Darwin, *On the Origin of Species*, London: (John Murray, 1859), 32-33.

²¹John Darling and Sven Erik Ordenbo, "Progressivism" in the *Blackwell Guide to the Philosophy of Education*, ed., N. Blake (New York: Blackwell, 2003), 288-308 (Hereafter will be referred as: Darling and Ordenbo, "Progressivism")

²²John Dewey, *My Pedagogic Creed*, 78.

²³John Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 72.

²⁴John Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 72-73.

²⁵John Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 73.

which means comprehensive acquisition of knowledge from different field.²⁶ For example, Science may need numbers to quantify data and good language to provide report, therefore science subjects depend on other subjects such as mathematics, language and other related subjects.²⁷ **Freedom**, means rendering chance for learners to select their learning needs and interest. Parents, teachers, elders and others have no power to decide over their children's learning needs and interest.²⁸ **Interaction**, since education is the result of experience, then Dewey advocates the importance of learners to interact with their learning environment. This helps learners to be aware of their environment, develop critical thinking, build inquisitive and speculative behavior among the learner, identify different social problems surrounding them and propose solution towards those social challenges. **Discussion**, is a free engagement of learners in academic conversation among themselves for sake of arriving to certain logical conclusion. Through debates in discussion learners develop reasonable arguments by formulating their own ideas, convince others and learn new issues from different world view. In his life time, Dewey established an ideal school which acted as a place where children can jointly engage in pursuit of knowledge in a peaceful way with their fellow students as a family while being provided with some moral teachings. To insist on moral development training of the child, Dewey writes that, "the best and deepest moral training is precisely that which one gets through having to enter into proper relation with others in a unity of work and thought."²⁹

Dewey's progressivism theory of education encourages modern methods of teachings that put the learner at the center of the learning process while considering their interest, ambition and needs. The methods involve, *project, experiments, learning by*

doing, discussion, exploration, critical thinking and discovery method. Furthermore, his theory enhance problem solving skills to the learners, discovery learning and utilization of social and natural resources for the benefit of the whole society. Dewey insists the design of education system with curriculum which foster freedom and interest of the learner as he writes that, "the beginning is made with child's expressive activities in dealing with the fundamental social material—food, shelter, clothing, and the direct modes of social communication like speech, writing, reading, drawing, modelling, molding etc."³⁰ Thus the curriculum in primary school should be organized according to the four-fold interest of the child in conversation, inquiry, construction and artistic expression.

3.0 The Role of Dewey's Progressivism Theory of Education in Ameliorating Tanzanian New E.T.P

Reforms in ETP proves that Tanzania has not yet managed to provide relevant education system which respond to the needs and problems of Tanzanian. On the other hand, Dewey's progressivism theory of education has been an influential education theory not only in modern era but also in contemporary time through enormous ideas such as practical education, problem solving skills, innovation, discoveries and other practical skills.³¹ Therefore, this part shows the contribution of Dewey's progressivism theory of education in improving Tanzanian new ETP particularly in terms of providing solution to different social problems and utilization of Tanzanian natural resources for the benefit of the whole society.

3.1 Problem Solving Skills and Social Reformation

Dewey is regarded as the founder of progressivism theory of education in the discourse of philosophy of education through his enormous and insightful ideas of viewing education as a means for social reformation. In his philosophies, he valued education as one of the powerful tool for social reformation and problem solving in the society. He is also among the founders of the social constructivism theory of education through his recognition of the society as a basis for mental transformation and an

²⁶John Dewey, *the Child and the Curriculum*. (London: The University of Chicago Press, 1966), 7. (Hereafter will be referred as: John Dewey, *the Child and the Curriculum*).

²⁷John Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 181.

²⁸John Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 16.

²⁹John Dewey, *The School and the Society*, 20.

³⁰John Dewey, *The Child and the Curriculum*, 9.

³¹John, Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 206.

active agent of economic and political development.³² For an effective social transformation, education system must help graduates to solve different social challenges by utilizing effectively their available resources for social benefit. Locke cemented the idea by writing that we become more perfect human being through perfecting our nature.³³ Education system which put much emphasis in the labor market does not help learners to be speculative and creative enough to interact effectively with nature. Hence, incorporating Dewey's educational ideas helps Tanzanians to be agents of social transformation rather than depending on the external support to comprehend their nature. Tanzania is rich with plenty of natural resources such as forest, minerals, natural gas and water which are useful for social and economic development however, they have not fully extracted because most graduates lack necessary skills to extract them.

3.2 Democracy and Freedom in Education

The new ETP emphasize most on the role of parents, society and government in general in the educative process while giving little emphasis on freedom and democracy of the children to decide and select their own education interest. This gives little chance for them to engage fully in their area of specialization and interest due to limited choices presented before them. Dewey's progressivism theory of education considers learners as having a great influence and chance to decide over their areas of interest in educative process. Education is purposely for the social benefit as well as individual realization. Quoting Plato, Dewey insist that, "The first is that such terms as the individual and the social conceptions of education are quite meaningless taken at large, or apart from their context. Plato had the ideal of an education which should equate individual realization and social coherency and stability."³⁴ Freedom to the learners in Tanzanian new ETP is manifested particularly in ordinary secondary education which is also compulsory to all learners. There are two main streams in secondary education namely; general education and vocation education whereby students are given chance

to opt for either the stream according to their ability and interest. Dewey's education theory insists learners to exercise their freedom to education in their early stages where they also have a great chance to reveal their natural tendencies, interest, talents and desires related to their future life.³⁵

3.3 Teaching Methodologies

Dewey in "My Pedagogic Creed" presented the two main motives in the educative process which determine the best methodological approach to use in teaching process. He viewed education process being mainly determined by psychological influences and socio-cultural influences. Nevertheless, He considered psychological side to be the basic as he articulates that, "Of these two sides the psychological is the basis. The child's own instincts and powers furnish the material and give the starting point for all education. Save as the efforts of the educator connect with some activity which the child is carrying on of his own initiative independent of the educator, education becomes reduced to a pressure from without."³⁶ Instincts and natural tendency help children to select their education interest while parents remain their guiders and supervisors towards realizing their desires. For the child's natural tendency to be actualized and give meaning, sociological factor is important because it is the platform for child's experience and interaction. Dewey asserts that, "the child has his own instincts and tendencies, but we do not know what these mean until we can translate them into their social equivalents.... we must also be able to project them into the future to see what their outcome and end will be."³⁷ Thus, the society is society must be able to accurately translate and interpret the child's capacities, interest and habits. In the context of social factor, the best method in facilitating the educative process includes projects, learning by doing, discussion, demonstration and construction of tangible ideas.³⁸ Actually Dewey preferred both theoretical and

³²John Dewey, *The School and the Society*, 15.

³³John Locke, *Two Treatises of Government*, ed. Peter Laslett. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1988), 123-124.

³⁴John, Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 102.

³⁵MoEST, *E.T. P, 2014, 2023 Edition*, 38.

³⁶John Dewey, *My Pedagogic Creed*, 4

³⁷John Dewey, *My Pedagogic Creed*, 5.

³⁸Morgan Williams, "ERIC- EJ11582558- John Dewey in the 21st Century," in *Journal of Inquiry & Action in Education*, v9, n1, 2017. 91-102, <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1158258.pdf>

practicability aspects which combines both psychological and sociological aspect. Therefore, modern methods in new Tanzanian ETP is useful for students to be more creative and discoveries of what goes around their social setting.

3.4 Education Formalities and Curriculum

Formalities in education sometimes leads to lack of flexibility especially for learners to exercise their innovation and discoveries. Contents outside the curriculum is less considered and even not prioritized. Unregulated formalities put learners to act like slaves who follow whatever is ordered even if it is not part of their interest. The new Tanzanian ETP exhibits some formalities such as prescribed number of years to accomplish certain education level regardless the achievement gained, certificate as the only verification to academic achievements, uniformity in curricula contents and other.³⁹ These formalities limits creativity for learners to exercise fully their abilities, talents and ambitions. Dewey education theory, suggests a less structured and flexible curriculum so as to allow learners to exercise their creativity. Morgan Williams in his article ‘*Dewey in the 21st Century*’ writes that; “When teachers plan for instruction, student’s interests will be taken into consideration and the curricular subjects will be integrated with an emphasis on project learning. The educational experience encompasses the intellectual, social, emotional, physical and spiritual growth of the whole child, not just academic growth.”⁴⁰

Montessori in his work, propagated the flexible system of education which facilitate teaching and training of learners in relation to their learning abilities, needs and interest as well as the system which allows learners to formulate their learning habits themselves instead of being confined in a single learning style.⁴¹ Pestalozzi advocated that, curriculum

stands as the direction of what learners needs to go about, and that it must not triggers freedom of the learners to go beyond the scope of the curriculum because learning is the result of both what we experience and what is in our mind including inborn abilities.⁴² Modern education theorists such as Paul Freire drawing ideas from John Dewey is against strict learning environment and old teaching and learning methodologies.⁴³ Paul Peterson, a Harvard University Professor and proponent of the homeschooling suggest that, learners may interact with their curricula contents, teachers and parents as their guider through different modern electronic devices at home without necessarily meeting together in a defined area to avoid wastage of time, travel expenses and any other challenges that may happen.⁴⁴

3.5 Vocation Education to Primary Level

The new ETP has specified and introduce vocation education stream in the formal education system starting from ordinary secondary level. This approach is good as it intends to increase education opportunities for learners with different abilities and interest. It also increases the chance for other students who fail to continue with general education to have an alternative way to join in vocation education streams so as to develop themselves in different skills and abilities. The challenge observed here is the late introduction of vocation education. Dewey’s education theory suggests educative process to begin during maturity which is the right time to engage in different playing activities which also speaks something about their natural tendencies and other psychological drives.⁴⁵ Furthermore, it is the time when children begin interacting among themselves and through interaction they convey some signals which speak something about their future interest. Therefore, vocational education need to extend to primary level

(Hereafter will be referred as: Morgan Williams, “ERIC-EJ11582558- John Dewey in the 21st Century,”)

³⁹MoEST, *Education and Training Policy, 2014:2023 Edition*, 37.

⁴⁰Morgan Williams, “ERIC- EJ11582558- John Dewey in the 21st Century,” 93-94.

⁴¹Maria Montessori, *The Montessori Method: Scientific Pedagogy as Applied to Child Education in the Children’s Houses*, trans. Anne E. George. (New York: Frederick A. Stokes Company, 1912), 79-80. (Hereafter will be referred as: Maria Montessori, *The Montessori Method*).

⁴²J.A. Green, ed., *Pestalozzi’s Education Writings* (London: Edward Arnold, 1912), 351. (Hereafter will be referred as: Green, ed., *Pestalozzi’s Education Writings*).

⁴³Paul Freire, *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. (London: [Penguin Classics, 2017], 24-25.

⁴⁴Paul E. Peterson, *Learning from Deregulation: The Asymmetric Political Response to School Choice*. (Brookings Institution Press, 2003). 36-38.

⁴⁵John, Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 288.

so as to help students master properly their educational aspirations. Dewey insists consistence in the learning experience where by the previous learning experience must positively influence the acquisition of the next learning experience.⁴⁶

Conclusion

For an effective provision of relevant education system in Tanzania, progressivism theory of education propagated by John Dewey is of great contribution especially in solving Tanzanian educational challenges that has been persisting for a number of years now. Embracing Dewey's education and philosophical ideas helps in ameliorating new Tanzanian ETP through promoting education system that responds to Tanzanian education challenges. Dewey's education theory promotes social and national development by encouraging critical thinking, innovation, creativity, experiments, discovery and practical education which enables learners to produce tangible products that supports and promote developments.

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⁴⁶John, Dewey, *Democracy and Education*, 163.

